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Integration of Family and School Interaction in the System of Teacher Training

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Abstract

The article substantiates the relevance of such research direction as the study of problems of interaction with the parents of students.

Postulating the existence of axiological crisis of the family and family relations in modern society, the crisis of family education, the authors examine some of the consequences of this crisis (complication of working with parents in general and a decrease in the activity of participation of parents in the educational process in particular) and as one of the possible solutions offer the appeal to the study of interaction with parents of students in the system of training teachers.

The question of theoretical justification and experimental development of a modular program for teachers' professional development as a necessary condition for increasing the level of interaction with parents of students is raised.

The leading method in the study of this problem was the method of designing the content of programs, structure of educational-thematic plan of teaching materials in the system of training teachers.

The program "Modern approaches to family education and the organization of parental education" was supported and implemented under the grant of the Federal project "New opportunities for everyone" of the national project "Education" in 2019.

The article presents the results of the research, the materials and practical tools, which can be used to build interaction with modern parents.

Keywords: interaction with parents, family education, parental education, professional development, professional and pedagogical competence.

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Introduction

The relevance of cooperation of educational organizations with students' parents is determined by the following existing levels: state and society, educational organizations, teacher education organizations, families, a higher school teacher.

At the level of society and the state:

- understanding the family as the most important institution of society, the basis of the state responsible for socializing new generations, considering parents as equal participants in the educational process and the designation of family issues in legal documents (the Federal Law "On education in the Russian Federation", "The Concept of the State Family Policy of the Russian Federation until 2025", "Basics of State Cultural Policy", "Strategy for the Development of Education in the Russian Federation for the Period until 2025", National project "Education", etc.).

Thus, the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" (2012) stipulates that parents are obliged to lay the foundations for the physical, moral and intellectual development of the child's personality, that is, parents are the main educators of their children.

Such direction as improving the pedagogical culture of parents, and in particular the formation of conscientious, responsible, informed and positive parenting is recorded in "The Concept of State Family Policy of the Russian Federation until 2025".

The main directions of the state cultural policy are defined as the revival of traditions of family education, providing parents with opportunities to receive affordable pedagogical and psychological assistance in raising children.

The priority of family education is stated in the "Strategy for the Development of Education in the Russian Federation for the period until 2025".

The need for psycho-pedagogical education of today's parents is formulated in the works of Danilyuk et al. (2014), Kozlov and Kondakov (2009) and others.

Let us emphasize that these normative documents provide for many things.

At the level of an educational organization:

- the significance of the organization of interaction between the educational organization and parents;

- availability of educational organization conditions for contact with parents;
- opportunities of the educational organization to provide real assistance to parents in raising a child.

At the level of a teacher of an educational organization:

- the importance of planning and implementing work with parents;
- requirements of the professional standard “Teacher (pedagogical activity in the field of preschool, primary general, basic general, secondary general education) (educator, teacher)” to the organization of work with parents;
- development of new forms and methods of interaction with parents;
- the existing problem, which is that teachers, especially young ones, experience significant problems (difficulties) in interacting with parents (based on the results of interviews and surveys).

At the level of a high school teacher:

- improving the quality of teaching and, accordingly, the training of future teachers, the formation of their professional competence, general and pedagogical culture, including such professionally determined requirements for the teacher’s personality as a highly developed sense of responsibility to parents for the education and upbringing of children (Sytina & Khabibova, 2019a).

At the family level:

- significant weakening of the institution of the family, its educational potential and healthy family traditions;
- changing family roles, reducing the overall level of parental competence, etc.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The aim of the research is to provide theoretical justification and experimental development of a modular program for teachers’ professional development as a necessary condition for increasing the level of interaction with students’ parents.

Research objectives:

- analyze the scientific literature on issues related to the research problem;
- conduct a logical and systematic analysis of educational material (programs, training plans, textbooks and manuals) of organizations that improve the skills of employees in the field of education;
- develop and implement an additional educational program of modular content in the conditions of the professional development system;

The leading idea of the study: necessary conditions for increasing the level of interaction with students' parents will be provided if:

- the training system will be implemented an additional educational program modular design, on the basis of the relationships increase the level of interaction with parents and increase the level of competence of teachers.

It is necessary to emphasize that this relationship occurs not only because of their direct interaction and functional directions, but also because of the necessary correspondence of the competence of the professional activity of the teacher and the educational standard.

Literature review

The analysis of scientific literature allowed us to identify the following areas related to this issue, as well as its research activity, so this is:

- questions of family education (Kapterev, 2005; Sukhomlinsky, 1988, etc.);
- issues of interaction between families and educational organizations (Shchurkova, 2007; Vygotsky, 1997, etc.);
- issues related to pedagogical education of parents, preparation of teachers to work with the family (Kapralova, 1980, Urbanskaya, 1986);
- the issues of additional professional education (Zagvyazinsky, 2006; Zeer, 2019, etc.).

Among the foreign researchers who studied the identified problems are Hamalyainen (1993), Kellerhals and Montandon (1991), whose works were devoted to the individual characteristics of socio-pedagogical problems of education.

Methodology

To solve the research tasks, the following methods were used:

- theoretical analysis of pedagogical literature on the research problem; logical and systematic analysis of educational materials (programs, training plans, textbooks and manuals) of organizations that improve the skills of employees in the field of education;
- study of legislative and regulatory documents on family education and parental education; designing the content of programs, structure of educational-thematic plan of teaching materials in the conditions of system of further training;
- survey of students and teachers.

The implementation of the program “Modern approaches to family education and the organization of parental education” was carried out within the framework of the grant of the Federal project “Training of citizens in continuing education programs in educational organizations implementing additional educational programs and vocational training programs”. This program was performed on the basis of the Institute of Additional Education. The Institute is a structural division of the Bashkir State University named after M. Akmulla.

Results

In order to test the assumptions made, we conducted a pedagogical experiment, during which a program was developed. Let us look at it in more detail.

In 2019, under the guidance of Professor Sytina from the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Bashkir State Pedagogical University named after M. Akmulla a professional development program for employees of educational organizations “Modern approaches to family education and the organization of parental education” (72 hours) was developed.

The program was implemented as part of the grant of the Federal project “Training citizens in continuing education programs in educational organizations that implement additional educational programs and vocational training programs” of the Federal project “New opportunities for everyone” of the national project “Education” in 2019.

The program is a successor to the main educational programs of higher education in the direction of training 44.03.01 Pedagogical Education (bachelor's degree) and the professional standard "Teacher (pedagogical activity in the field of preschool, primary general, basic general, secondary general education) (educator, teacher)".

The program is developed on the basis of cooperation with educational organizations that form a request for educational programs in accordance with the needs of highly qualified specialists with a certain set of competencies, timely updating of the program in accordance with the needs of the real economy and meets the needs of employers.

The direction of the program is to improve professional and pedagogical competencies necessary for professional activity and professional development in the field of pedagogy of family education and the organization of parental education. The program provides both classroom and remote forms of classes.

Students of advanced training courses had the opportunity to engage in solving pedagogical situations, imitate professional responsibilities for effective interaction between the family and the educational organization; design and conduct pedagogically appropriate work with parents at the present stage; develop competence in the aspect of justification of expediency and choice of methods and forms of modern parental education.

Before proceeding to the content of the program, it is necessary to identify a number of concepts that carry a large semantic load. Without giving an analysis of the set of conceptual interpretations of the selected concepts available in scientific research, we will define the following categories. So, we adhere to the following definitions.

Focusing on the fact that the concept of "interaction" is a philosophical category, Kokhanovsky believes that "the interaction itself should not be understood on an external, superficial, rational level..." (2003, p. 156).

Defining family education as an educational system under construction in the family, Mardahaev (2014, p. 173) emphasizes that "such a system is formed on the basis of personal experience of parents received in their families, "enriched" by the data of literature and the advice of other people who were listened to in the process of educational activity. In essence, any system of family education is nothing more than a manifestation of the subjectivity of the parent in its understanding and implementation".

Highlighting pedagogical education as a form of cooperation between teachers of educational organizations and parents, parent universal education, as believed by Naumenko (2017, p. 44), "involves informing

parents about age-related changes in the development of the child's personality and ways of interacting with it, built in the context of the life of the subjects of interaction in accordance with the values of culture. Pedagogical education differs from any other education not only in its content, but also in the way it is organized - first of all, it is the exchange of pedagogical experience”.

The professional development program is of a modular design.

Module 1. Topical issues of family education reveal the traditional and modern functions of the family, the role of child-parent relations, abnormal family crises and their impact on children, the concept and types of family education, methods and means of family education, typical mistakes of parents in family education, cooperation as an optimal tactic of family education of children, the possibilities of pedagogical technologies in family education.

Module 2. Education as a basis for supporting cooperation and motivating parents allows us to consider the organization of effective interaction between the family and the educational organization (stages, forms, algorithm of organization and conduct). Parent meeting as an actual-active-activity form of parent education (algorithm of organization and conduct). Features of planning and conducting pedagogically appropriate work with parents. Interaction with participants of the educational process in the framework of extracurricular activities. Innovative forms of interaction between the educational organization and parents.

The final assessment of the professional development program is the development and defense of an innovative project aimed at parent education (as one of the areas of interaction with parents). The structural elements of the project are: goals and objectives, pedagogical techniques, forms, original ideas for achieving the goal, as well as their justification; expected results (qualitative and quantitative), criteria for determining results.

Implementation of system-activity and personal-oriented approaches to training students in the system of professional development: exchange of experience, project development, discussions, etc.

As a result of mastering the program, students have improved the following professional competencies:

- readiness to interact with participants of the educational process;
- ability to use modern methods and technologies of training and diagnostics;
- ability to design educational programs.

Let us look at them in more detail.

Competence: readiness to interact with participants in the educational process involves the use of constructive educational efforts of parents (legal representatives) of students, assistance to the family in solving issues of child rearing. The nature of skills is the creation in educational groups (class, circle, section, etc.) of different age child-adult communities of students, their parents (legal representatives) and teaching staff. The necessary knowledge should include the basics of teaching methods, the main principles of the activity approach, types and techniques of modern pedagogical technologies. The content of performing labor functions: using constructive educational efforts of parents (legal representatives) of students, helping the family in solving issues of child rearing, developing (together with other specialists) and implementing together with parents (legal representatives) programs for individual child development, etc. The ability to develop (master) and apply modern psychological and pedagogical technologies based on knowledge of the laws of personal development and behavior in real and virtual environments and knowledge of the basic laws of age development, stages and crises of development and socialization of the individual, indicators and individual characteristics of life trajectories and their possible deviations, methods of their diagnostics correspond to such competence as the ability to use modern methods and technologies of training and diagnostics. Labor functions include the implementation of professional activities in accordance with the requirements of the Federal state educational standards for preschool, primary general, basic general, and secondary general education.

Competence: the ability to design educational programs involves the development (together with other specialists) and implementation, together with parents (legal representatives), of programs for the individual development of the child. The necessary skills and knowledge are the formation of a child-adult community and the basic laws of family relations that allow us to work effectively with the parent community, respectively.

In our opinion, it is reasonable to include in the program such issues as interaction with participants of the educational process in the framework of extracurricular activities.

It should be emphasized that extracurricular activities are:

- a mechanism for expanding and improving educational services that allows educational organizations to achieve a new quality of education and, accordingly, the competitiveness of Russian education (the level of the educational organization).

- the method of self-realization of the teacher (independence in filling out specific content of extracurricular activities, the use of a variety of its forms, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies that ensure personal development and formation of students), etc. (Sytina & Khabibova, 2019b).

Understanding all the complexities of extracurricular activities as a multidimensional phenomenon that predetermines the difficulties faced by specialists, both at the theoretical and practical levels, we, however, allocate extracurricular activities not so much as a means of organizing interaction with the parents of students, but as an important resource for activating the participation of parents in the educational process (Khabibova & Sytina, 2019).

Here are the results of a survey (N=400) of satisfaction with the educational program “Modern approaches to family education and organization parent education”.

1. Distribution of answers to the question “Your attitude to the information received on the courses, to its significance for You”

Table 1

Answer options	Total among respondents
The information offered in the classroom is new, it leads to new conclusions, and allows you to take a new look at the situation in your field of activity	74 %
The information presents only introductory knowledge, but will not be superfluous in my work	3.3 %
Classes on the course allow you to practically master new knowledge, methods, forms, ways of working under the program “Modern approaches to family education and the organization of parental education”	13.3 %
This information allows you to participate in the organization of experimental innovations in this area	7.4 %
The proposed information is available to you from other sources, and the classes are not of interest to you.	2 %

2. Distribution of answers to the question “What are the results of training courses”?

Table2

Answer options	Total among respondents
They helped to define their own pedagogical position on the issues raised	22 %

Increased my level of understanding of the issues discussed	41 %
Aroused a desire to learn the best teaching experience of colleagues	24 %
Helped in determining the individual trajectory of self-improvement	10 %
Did not have a significant impact on the development of my professionalism	2 %
Did not meet my expectations	1 %

3. How satisfied were you with your training?

Table 3

	Completely	Partially	Dissatisfied
Novelty of educational material	90 %	9 %	1 %
Volume of theoretical material	88 %	10 %	2 %
Practice-oriented training	89 %	9 %	2 %
Methods of teaching, learning	90 %	9 %	1 %
Teacher-to-student ratio	88 %	10 %	2 %
Organization of the educational process	92 %	7 %	1 %
Equipment classes with remote educational technologies, didactic material	89 %	9 %	2 %

4. Distribution of answers to the question “Assess the level of your own readiness to implement the tasks considered in the course in practice”

Table 4

Answer options	Total among respondents
Basic minimum level	9 %
Ready for practical use of the available information	65 %
I am ready to share my experience with my colleagues	20 %
Not ready for practical implementation of the issues under consideration	3 %
I need individual assistance to improve my skills in this area	3 %

5. Distribution of answers to the question “Can you use the knowledge gained during training in your practical work”?

Table 5

Answer options	Total among respondents
Yes	84 %
It is hard to say	14 %
No	2 %

Discussions

We would like to highlight the problem of choosing the forms of interaction between the family and the educational organization among the most pressing issues of discussion. So, at the initial stage of training courses, we conducted a survey of practicing teachers (N=400 people), aimed at identifying pedagogical difficulties in the context of interaction between the family and the educational organization.

Among the seventeen suggested forms of interaction, the most effective forms of working with parents (in terms of activity and in terms of the pedagogical value of participants), practicing teachers identified such forms as: parent meetings; individual consultations.

Another position is held by students, future teachers (survey (N=200), who suggested such forms of interaction with parents as: participation of parents in Internet forums, blitz surveys; development of an Internet page (class Portfolio), etc.

We believe that the issue here is not so much in the forms of interaction with parents (traditional, innovative). The main research issue is the development and implementation of modern methods and techniques that help to activate the attention of parents on certain issues and promote mutual understanding between parents and teachers. Finally, it should be recalled that the organizational form of parent-teacher conferences includes workshops and presentations of families (traditions, views on education), various creative forms, etc.

The identified problems of interaction with the parents of students require a deep understanding. It is obvious that the existing methods and methods of interaction do not meet the needs of either modern society or modern education.

Conclusion

This article presents the results of theoretical substantiation and experimental development of a modular program for teachers' professional development as a necessary condition for increasing the level of interaction with students' parents.

The implementation of the program "Modern approaches to family education and the organization of parental education" contributed to the improvement of pedagogical competencies necessary for professional activity, and professional development in the field of pedagogy of family education and organization of parental education.

The article presents the results of the research (development and implementation of the program), the materials and practical tools, which can be used to build interaction with modern parents, taking into account the peculiarities of the educational situation of the organization, as well as the implementation of professional development organizations in practice.

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